

Preparation of Borate, Tungstate, Molybdate and other Jellies and Study of Mercuri-sulphosalicylic Acid Jellies.

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In previous communications from these laboratories (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 168, 214; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587) we have investigated the conditions of formation of various hydroxide, arsenate, phosphate, molybdate, tungstate and borate jellies and have also studied the changes in viscosity and hydrogen ion concentrations during the process of their gelation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 391). In this paper, we are recording the methods of preparation of the following jellies which have been obtained by us for the first time :

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|-------------------------|----------------------|
| 1. Chromic tungstate. | 4. Zirconium borate. |
| 2. Ferric tungstate. | 5. Cerio arsenate. |
| 3. Zirconium molybdate. | 6. Cerio borate. |

Our results with the jellies of mercurisulphosalicylic acid and its sodium salts are also recorded in this paper.

Chromic Tungstate Jellies.

It appears that chromium salts have less tendency to form jellies when compared with iron salts. An attempt to prepare molybdate or borate jellies has so far been unsuccessful and the only jellies of chromium salts that have been obtained are chromium arsenate and phosphate.

When sodium tungstate solution is added to chromic chloride solution, a bulky greenish-white precipitate is formed, which slightly dissolves on shaking at the room temperature (25-30°) even when chromic chloride is present in large excess. However if the mixture is warmed and shaken, a sufficient amount of chromic tungstate is peptised and it forms a clear transparent solution. If this solution is now allowed to dialyse for about ten days, a translucent sol is

obtained which sets to a jelly on addition of potassium sulphate. To $M/1.5$ -chromic chloride solution, a 15 per cent. solution of sodium tungstate was added and the mixture was warmed and shaken. The amount of sodium tungstate was added so long as the precipitate formed could be redissolved on warming. The solution still contained much of the free chromic chloride, and it was dialysed for ten days, when a translucent sol was obtained. This sol sets to a jelly when kept in a Jens bottle for about a month. The sol gives jellies readily on adding potassium sulphate.

Concentration of the sol = 23.86 g. chromic tungstate per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c.

Total volume was made 3 c.c. or 6 c.c. each time by adding the requisite amount of water.

TABLE I.

Potassium sulphate.	Total volume.	Observations.
$N/20-1.0$ a.c.	3 c.c.	Gelatinous precipitate.
0.5	3	Gelatinous precipitate.
0.3	3	Sets to green, opaque, loose jelly in 30 minutes, soon synerises.
0.1	3	Sets to firm opalescent jelly within 24 hours; syneresis not marked.
$N/50-0.5$	3	Sets in 1 hour 45 minutes to opaque, loose jelly, which synerises soon.
0.4	3	Sets in 25 hours to firm jelly with slight syneresis.
0.3	3	Sets in 24 hours with no syneresis.
0.2	3	Sets in 2 days with no syneresis
0.5	6	Sets in 24 hours; no syneresis.
0.4	6	Sets in 24 hours; no syneresis.
0.3	6	Sets to translucent jelly in 24 hours.
0.2	6	Sets in 2 days to firm translucent jelly.

Ferric Tungstate Jelly.

In a previous paper (*loc. cit.*), we have shown that when suitable concentrations of sodium tungstate are added to ferric chloride solution in excess, the mixture sets to a yellow opaque jelly. We have now observed that more transparent jellies are obtained when a mixture of sodium tungstate and ferric chloride taken in excess is

dialysed and the sol thus obtained is coagulated with electrolytes. To 75 c.c. of 0.929M-ferric chloride solution was added a solution of 16.5 g. sodium tungstate ($\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with vigorous shaking and slight warming, and the volume was made up to a litre. The mixture was filtered and dialysed for 6 days. The clear sol so obtained sets to translucent jellies on the addition of suitable amounts of electrolytes.

Concentration of the sol = 21.68 g. ferric tungstate per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time = 4 c.c.

Total volume = 5 c.c.

TABLE II.

Electrolyte.	Observations.
<i>N-Potassium chloride.</i>	
0.3 c.c.	Translucent jelly in 1 day ; syneresis starts after 3 days.
0.4	" " "
0.6	Loose jelly in 2 hours.
0.8	Loose opaque jelly in 45 mins.
1.0	No jelly ; coagulated gelatinous mass.
<i>N/20-Potassium sulphate.</i>	
0.2 c.c.	Sets in 1 day to a translucent jelly.
0.4	" " "
0.5	Sets in 6 minutes to a jelly.
0.5	Sets to a jelly in 2 mins.
0.6	Sets to a jelly in 1 min.

Most of the tungstate jellies prepared are loose and translucent with slight opalescence and have marked tendency towards syneresis.

Zirconium Molybdate Jellies.

No arsenate or phosphate jellies of zirconium have yet been reported. When potassium arsenate or phosphate is added to a solution of zirconium nitrate, a white gelatinous precipitate is formed which can be peptised only slightly by adding excess of zirconium nitrate. For this reason, it is not possible to obtain a sol of either zirconium arsenate or phosphate of suitable concentrations. Only bulky white opaque jellies of arsenate or phosphate are sometimes

obtained, when the mixture of potassium arsenate or phosphate and zirconium nitrate is warmed up to 90°. No jellies of fine texture have yet been obtained.

When potassium molybdate solution is added to zirconium nitrate solution, a white precipitate of zirconium molybdate is obtained, which is easily dissolved by an excess of zirconium nitrate on shaking. In this way, a sufficient amount of zirconium molybdate can be peptised, and a concentrated sol could be obtained. This sol on dialysis gives suitable jellies when coagulated with electrolytes. If the sol is dialysed for a long time, it either sets on the parchment paper or gives a transparent jelly on standing for some days without the addition of electrolytes. Some of the jellies prepared by the coagulation of the sol by potassium chloride, develop opalescence, and may even become opaque.

To 70 c.c. of $M/1.38$ -zirconium nitrate solution was added a 10 per cent. solution of potassium molybdate, till the precipitate obtained just dissolved in the excess of zirconium nitrate. The total volume of the mixture was made 200 c.c. and the sol thus obtained was dialysed for 36 hours. Strength of the sol = 50.88 g. zirconium molybdate per litre.

TABLE III.

Total volume = 4 c.c.

Zirconium molybdate sol.	Electrolyte.	Observations.
	N-KCl	
2 c.c.	0.3 c.c.	Sets to a transparent jelly in 3 hours.
2	0.4	Sets to a transparent jelly in 30 minutes.
2	0.6	Sets to an opalescent jelly in 20 minutes.
3	0.2	Clear solution, no jelly.
3	0.3	Sets to a transparent jelly in 90 minutes.
3	0.4	Sets to an opalescent jelly in 6 minutes.
3	0.6	Opalescent jelly in 2 mins.
3	0.8	" " " 1 min.
3	1.0	Immediately set to an opaque jelly.
	N/5-K ₂ SO ₄	
2	0.2	Clear solution, no jelly.
2	0.3	Translucent jelly in 2½ hrs.
2	0.4	" " " 6 mins.
2	0.5	" " " immediately; slight syneresis observed.
3	0.1	Transparent jelly in 3½ hrs.
3	0.3	" " " 2 hrs.
3	0.4	" " " 30 mins.
3	0.5	Opalescent jelly in 12 mins.

Zirconium Borate Jellies.

Zirconium borate jellies have been prepared in the same way as molybdate jellies. A hot concentrated solution of borax was added to 70 c.c. of $M/1.88$ -zirconium nitrate solution till the precipitate of zirconium borate obtained just dissolved in the excess of zirconium nitrate. The total volume of the solution was made 200 c.c. and allowed to dialyse for 3 days.

Concentration of the sol = 84.62 g. zirconium borate per litre.

This sol gives transparent or opalescent jellies when coagulated by electrolytes.

TABLE IV.

Total volume = 4 c.c.

Zirconium borate sol.	Electrolytes.	Observations.
	<i>N-KCl</i>	
2 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	Opalescent jelly in 1 day.
2	0.4	Transparent jelly in 7 minutes, which develops opalescence soon.
2	0.5	Translucent jelly in 3 minutes.
2	0.7	Opalescent jelly in 1 minute.
2	0.9	Immediately sets to an opaque jelly.
3	0.1	No jelly.
3	0.3	Transparent jelly in 20 minutes
3	0.5	Transparent jelly in 3 minutes.
3	0.7	Opalescent jelly in 1 minute.
3	0.9	Immediately sets to an opaque jelly.
	<i>N/5-K₂SO₄</i>	
2	0.2	Clear solution, no jelly.
2	0.3	" " "
2	0.5	Transparent jelly in 1 hour.
2	0.6	Transparent jelly in 10 minutes.
2	0.8	Translucent jelly immediately formed: syneresis starts at once.
3	0.5	Transparent jelly in 40 minutes.
3	0.4	" " "
3	0.3	Clear solution, no jelly.
3	0.2	" "

It has been observed in the case of both zirconium molybdate and borate, that the jellies are more readily obtained when sols are coagulated by potassium chloride but these jellies develop opalescence on standing. When sols are coagulated by potassium sulphate, the jellies are more transparent and do not develop marked opalescence. More syneresis is observed in the case of potassium sulphate than in the case of potassium chloride.

Ceric Arsenate Jelly.

When a solution of potassium arsenate is added to ceric ammonium nitrate solution in small quantities and allowed to stand, yellow opalescence develops after a time and under suitable concentrations the whole mass sets to a fine transparent or opaque jelly. Some of the jellies are loose and in almost all the cases, they undergo syneresis within 12—24 hours and finally break up.

To a 10 per cent. solution of ceric ammonium nitrate, various quantities of potassium arsenate (18 per cent. solution) were added, and the volume was made the same in all the cases by adding the requisite amount of water. The observations are recorded in the following table.

TABLE V.

Total volume = 4.5 c.c.		
Ceric ammonium nitrate.	Potassium arsenate.	Observations.
4 c.c.	0.1 c.c.	No jelly.
4	0.15	Loose jelly in 1 hour.
4	0.2	Firm transparent jelly with opalescence in 15 minutes.
4	0.25	Translucent jelly in 3 minutes.
4	0.3	Yellow opaque jelly in 1 minute.
4	0.4	Opaque jelly in $\frac{1}{2}$ minute.
3	0.3	Loose, translucent jelly in 1 minute; soon breaking.
3	0.25	" " "
3	0.2	Loose translucent jelly in 3 mins.
3	0.15	Firm translucent jelly in 5 mins.

Ceric Borate Jellies.

When a solution of borax is added to a solution of ceric ammonium nitrate, a yellowish-white precipitate is obtained which readily dissolves on shaking, if the ceric ammonium nitrate is in excess. If the mixture of these two substances is allowed to stand for some time, the contents are generally precipitated, though in some cases, loose unstable jellies may also form.

The clear solution formed by mixing 100 c.c. of 10 per cent. ceric ammonium nitrate and 35 c.c. of 15 per cent. borax solution was dialysed for 24 hours. The sol thus obtained not only gave a jelly on treatment with potassium sulphate; but also on keeping for some time in a Jena bottle, its viscosity increases continuously and in the next 24 hours, it sets completely to an opalescent jelly. Another sol was prepared by mixing only 30 c.c. of 15 per cent. borax solution to ceric ammonium nitrate. The mixture on dialysis gave a clear sol in 24 hours. This sol was quite stable and could be kept for weeks and gave jellies only on the addition of potassium sulphate. The results are recorded below.

TABLE VI.

Concentration of the sol=36.44 g. ceric borate per litre.
Total volume=5 c.c.

Ceric borate sol.	Potassium sulphate.	Observations.
3 c.c.	N/20—1.0 c.c.	Firm translucent jelly in 24 hours.
3	1.3	Loose jelly in 24 hours.
3	1.4	Loose jelly in 2½ hours.
3	1.5	Loose jelly in 1½ hours.
3	1.6	Gelatinous precipitate.
3.5	1.5	Translucent firm jelly in 1 hour 45 mins.
4.0	N/5—0.4 c.c.	Firm transparent jelly in 3 hours.
4.0.	0.5	Transparent jelly with opalescence in ¼ hour.

Mercurisulphosalicylic Acid Jellies.

Berkmann and Zocher (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 309, 922) studied the anisotropy and double refraction of mercurisulphosalicylic acid salts. Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*Kolloid Chem. Beih.* 1926, 23, 242)

studied the colloidal properties of complex mercuri-derivatives of sulphosalicylic acid. In a previous communication (*loc. cit.*) we have studied the changes in viscosity during the process of gelation, when freshly precipitated mercuric oxide is dissolved in sulphosalicylic acid solution. There we observed that for the first six hours, there was no marked increase in the viscosity and then for the next three hours, a regular exponential increase with time was observed, and this was followed by an abrupt increase in the viscosity till the solution sets to a transparent jelly.

When freshly precipitated mercuric oxide is dissolved in sulphosalicylic acid solution, perfectly transparent jellies are obtained within 24 hours, if the concentration of mercuric oxide is regulated. These jellies are perfectly stable and do not undergo marked syneresis. With higher concentrations of mercuric oxide, opaque jellies are produced. The jellies of mercurisulphosalicylic acid are heat-reversible. On being dried on a water-bath, a white powder is obtained and this gives a viscous sol when shaken with water, and when the concentration is suitable, sets to a transparent or translucent jelly. 1.5 Mols. of mercuric oxide were dissolved in 1 mol. of sulphosalicylic acid and the mixture was dried on a water-bath. The powder of mercurisulphosalicylic acid sets to jellies when dissolved in water in proper concentrations as shown in the following table.

TABLE VII.

Total volume=5 c.c.

Mercurisulphosalicylic acid.	Observations.
0.1 g.	No jelly within 24 hours.
0.3	" " "
0.5	Transparent jelly within 40 minutes.
0.7	Transparent jelly in 20 minutes.
0.9	Turbid jelly in 10 minutes.

Most of these jellies are transparent but they are not uniform because it becomes very difficult to get a clear homogeneous solution of mercurisulphosalicylic acid at such concentrations. Like soap jellies, the jellies of mercurisulphosalicylic acid so prepared melt on heating and again set on cooling as is shown in the following table.

TABLE VIII.

Total volume = 5 c.c.

Mercurisulphosalicylic acid.	Time of setting.	Time of setting after once being melted and cooled.
0.5 g.	40 min.	15 min.
0.7	20	2
0.9	10	Instantaneous setting.

It will be seen from the above table that the time of setting of the jelly when once melted is much less than the original setting time.

The sodium salt of mercurisulphosalicylic acid is prepared by adding 1 mol. of sodium hydroxide to 1 mol. of mercurisulphosalicylic acid. If to a solution of mercurisulphosalicylic acid, the requisite amount of sodium hydroxide is added, and the mixture dried on a water-bath, a white powder is obtained. It has been observed that this white powder of sodium mercurisulphosalicylate loses its power of setting to a jelly when re-dissolved in water. In this respect it appears to be heat-irreversible and differs from the original mercurisulphosalicylic acid. All concentrations between 0.1 g. and 0.6 g. of this sodium salt in 5 c.c. total volume have been tried but no jelly could be obtained with this substance.

The jellies of the sodium salt can be obtained by adding the calculated amount of sodium hydroxide to mercurisulphosalicylic acid, when the concentration is suitable. The comparative results for the time of setting of the original acid jelly and also its sodium salt are given in the following table.

TABLE IX.

Total volume = 5 c.c.

For the preparation of sodium salt, for each 0.1 g. of mercurisulphosalicylic acid, 0.116 c.c. of 2.08*N*-sodium hydroxide has been used.

Mercurisulphosalicylic acid.	Time of setting for the acid jelly.	Time of setting for the sodium salt jelly.
0.1 g.	No jelly in 24 hours.	No jelly in 24 hours.
0.3	" " "	10 min.
0.5	40 min.	8 min.
0.7	20 min.	5 min.

The results recorded in the above table show that the sodium salt more readily sets to jelly than the original acid of the same concentration. However, it has been observed that the jellies of the sodium salt are more opaque than the corresponding acid jellies. It

clearly shows that in the sodium salt the agglomeration tendency of the particles is more prominent than the hydration tendency, and this is probably the reason why once dried the sodium salt does not set when re dissolved in water. The jellies of the sodium salt also melt when heated and re set on cooling.

TABLE X

Total volume = 5 c c

Amount of mercurisulphosalicylic acid in salt jelly	Time of setting of the sodium jelly	Time of setting after once being melted and cooled
0.3 g	10 mins	20 mins
0.5	8	11
0.7	5	5

The above table shows that the time of setting of the jelly when once melted is greater than the original setting time. This also shows that in contrast to acid jellies, the hydration tendency of the sodium salt particles is much less, as was also seen from the heat irreversibility of the sodium salt jelly.

For the preparation of these acid or salt jellies, a sufficiently high concentration of mercurisulphosalicylic acid is required. But the jellies so prepared are very stable and do not exhibit marked syneresis. However, more dilute jellies can be obtained if the colloidal solution of the mercurisulphosalicylic acid is coagulated by electrolytes.

In the preparation of the following jellies 4 c c of 1 per cent solution of mercurisulphosalicylic acid were used and the total volume was made 5 c c in all the cases.

TABLE XI

Electrolyte	Observations
<i>N Potassium nitrate</i>	
0.3 c c.	Translucent jelly in 5 minutes
0.5	Translucent jelly in 2 minutes, soon synerising
<i>N Potassium sulphate</i>	
0.2 c c	Translucent jelly in 1 hour
0.3	Transparent jelly in 40 minutes
0.4	Transparent jelly in 2 minutes
0.6	Opalescent jelly in 1 minute
0.8	
1.0	Translucent "jelly" immediately— which soon undergoes syneresis
<i>N/10 Barium nitrate</i>	
0.2 c c	No jelly
0.3	Opaque jelly in 1 minute, soon synerising.
0.5	Opaque jelly immediately, soon synerising

When to the solution of mercurisulphosalicylic acid, potassium, lithium or barium chloride is added, the dissolution of the colloidal phase appears to occur and a clear solution which is less viscous than the original sol is obtained and this does not coagulate on adding concentrated solutions of potassium sulphate or barium nitrate.

The sodium salt of mercurisulphosalicylic acid yields a negatively charged sol which sets to a jelly on the addition of electrolytes. To 1 g. of mercurisulphosalicylic acid were added 1.16 c.c. of 2.08 N-sodium hydroxide solution, and the total volume was made up to 100 c.c. For the preparation of the jellies of this sodium mercurisulphosalicylate, 4 c.c. of the solution were taken each time, and varying quantities of potassium sulphate or barium nitrate were added ; the total volume was kept 5 c.c. in each case. The results are recorded below.

TABLE XII.

Electrolyte.	Observations.
<i>N-Potassium sulphate.</i>	
0.2 c.c.	Translucent jelly in 10 minutes.
0.3	" " 6 "
0.4	" " 3 "
0.6	" " 3 "
1.0	Opaque precipitate.
<i>N/10-Barium nitrate.</i>	
0.05 c.c.	No jelly.
0.1	Translucent jelly after 24 hours.
0.2	Precipitate in 24 hours ; no jelly.
0.3	Opaque loose jelly in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, soon synerising.

Comparing the results of this table with those of the previous one on the acid jellies, it will be seen that at the same concentration of the jelly and the coagulating electrolyte, the time of setting for the acid jelly is much greater than for the sodium salt jelly. The jellies of both the acid and the salt are opalescent and undergo marked syneresis. They are not so stable as those prepared without the addition of electrolytes. The colloidal solution of sodium salt also undergoes dissolution when chloride ions are added to it.

Wo. Ostwald and Mertens (*loc. cit.*) have observed that Cl-, Br-, CN-, and CNS-ions exert "dissolving" influence on sols of mercurisulphosalicylic acid derivatives, and they assume a true chemical

combination with the formation of a compound of the type sodium 3-chloromercuri-5-sulphosalicylate when mercurisulphosalicylic acid is mixed with sodium chloride. Such examples of chlorination by the mere addition of sodium chloride are not familiar in organic chemistry. What appears to be more probable is that the addition of chloride ions displaces the mercury of sulphosalicylic acid derivatives. This view is further supported by the fact that the mercuriation of sulphosalicylic acid is far easily conducted by freshly precipitated mercuric oxide free from chloride ions than by mercuric chloride. The crystalline compound, decomposing at 240° which Wo. Ostwald takes to be a chloromercuri-compound, appears to be a mixture of mercuric chloride and sodium sulphosalicylate.

Summary.

1. Jellies of chromic tungstate, ferric tungstate, zirconium molybdate, zirconium borate and ceric borate have been prepared for the first time by coagulation of the sols obtained by dialysing the mixtures of chromic chloride, ferric chloride or ceric ammonium nitrate and sodium tungstate, potassium molybdate or borax. Ceric arsenate jelly was obtained by mixing the solution of potassium arsenate and ceric ammonium nitrate.

2. The jellies of mercurisulphosalicylic acid were prepared by three methods; (a) by dissolving the freshly precipitated mercuric oxide in sulphosalicylic acid, which gives stable transparent jellies; (b) by re-dissolving the dried powder of mercurisulphosalicylic acid at high concentrations; and (c) by coagulating the dilute sol of mercurisulphosalicylic acid with electrolytes when translucent or opaque jellies are obtained which undergo marked syneresis.

3. The jellies of sodium mercurisulphosalicylate are heat-irreversible and it has been observed that the jelly-forming tendency of the salt is less than that of the acid.

4. The jellies of mercurisulphosalicylic acid and its salt melt when heated and re-set on cooling like soap jellies.

5. The 'dissolving influence' of chloride ions is ascribed to the displacement of mercury from the mercurisulphosalicylic acid derivative and not to the formation of chloromercuri-derivatives as Wo. Ostwald thinks.